

Research Article

Songket Brooch: The Potential of Malay Songket Motif in Jewellery Generation Ideas

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Abstract: *The research was conducted with the purpose of identifying the potential and significance of Malay Songket motif (Tampuk Manggis) in generation ideas from the context of contemporary jewellery designs. With the main objective to assist researchers in identifying, distinguishing as well as appreciating the Malay Songket motif, this study focused on translating those to creative and innovative designs specifically in contemporary brooch. The Double Diamond method was employed as it is the most befitting in achieving the aims of the study. This model has four main phases which are: 1) Search, 2) Define, 3) Develop and 4) Deliver. This research has 2 phases. Phase 1: Songket Brooch production by Internship students at The Bench Studio and fully completed. Phase 2: User feedback which will be carried out in the next stage. The Copyright Songket Brooch is now in the MyIPO app.*

Keywords: Songket Motif, generation idea, product design process, jewellery

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1. INTRODUCTION

Motifs are decorative elements in art objects, such as songket. Motifs are made up of geometric patterns and have specific arrangements and techniques. Songket weaving is one of the Malay handicraft arts that is in high demand not only for its beautiful fabric but also for its aesthetic value, as well as the meaning implied in it, which has made it a cultural symbol for Malays since ancient times.

Songket patterns or flower motifs are inspired from observations of nature and surrounding objects (Ab. Aziz, Arba'iyah, 2015). As such, songket motifs are based on flora, fauna, cosmos, nature, geometry, food and calligraphy. The Songket Brooch product takes the Tampuk Manggis Motif (Tapak Manggis) as a study material because it is seen from the point of view of uniqueness, aesthetics, and common motifs in Malay weaving. Tampuk Manggis is derived from the mangosteen fruit. Eight identical petals, grouped tightly together, encircle the little cross-shaped center of this pattern.

Figure 1: Motif Tenunan Melayu

(Source: <https://academyofsingaporeteachers.moe.edu.sg/mlcs/resources/hikmah-melayu/hikmah-melayu-1>)

According to Daud, M. Z., Ibrahim, M., Yaakob, N. H. M., Anuar, N. S. M., & Omar, M. (2022) This research shows various art formalistic aspects of jewellery that can be described as art elements, such as lines, shape, form, texture, colors, and space as well as design principles, such as harmony, contrast, emphasis, balance, variety, rhythm, and unity. Therefore, this motif is processed and designed into a Songket Brooch based on design elements and principles.

This study focuses on the category of contemporary jewelry in which it belongs to the wearer group. Contemporary jewelry began in the 1960s and has evolved to the present day. According to Justyna Stasiewicz (2015):

Contemporary Jewelry, also known as Modernist Jewelry, has gone far beyond the craft, becoming virtually another discipline of art, a tool to express the author's statement. Contemporary Jewelry also the phenomenon of costume jewelry appeared, mass-produced, cheap, made from new materials and closely associated with the wave of pop art. Brooch is a clothing ornament with a hinged pin and catch.

Chains, bracelets, earrings, and other types of jewellery are available for men, women, and children of all ages and can be worn for a variety of reasons (Anuar, N.S.M., Daud, M. Z., & Ibrahim, M. 2021). Daud, M.Z., Ibrahim, M., & Anuar, N.S.M. (2021) states that the Malacca Sultanate used gemstone jewellery for the first time in 1400 AD. Brooch is a clothing ornament with a hinged pin and catch. The selection of brooch because by wearing brooches as a fashion accessory to stay on trend or to make their outfit more appealing.

Figure 1: The Queen's Aquamarine Brooches

(Source: <https://www.thecourtjeweller.com/2020/03/the-queens-aquamarine-brooches.html>)

2. METHOD

2.1 Double Diamond Model in Jewellery

Double Diamond is a process model created by the Design Council, a British organization, in 2005. This model was used in a paper entitled *Electronic Jewellery: The Coalescing of Electronic Devices and Contemporary Jewellery* (Muda, M. S., Anuar, N. S. M., Daud, M. Z., Jalaludin, M. F., & Rosly, R. 2022). Therefore, this Model provides a graphical representation of the design process. The Double Diamond model is seen as appropriate to be applied in this study.

Figure 3: Model Double Diamond, yang dibangunkan oleh Design Council UK tahun 2005 (Source: <https://innovationenglish.sites.ku.dk/model/double-diamond-2/>)

According to Maciej Lipiec (2019) the design process should have four main phases of each design process: 1) Find (identify, research, and understand the problem), 2) Define (limit and define a clear problem to solve), 3) Develop (focus and develop solutions), and 4) Deliver (test and evaluate, prepare concepts for production and launch).

According to Rahim, M.I.C., Ibrahim, M., Daud, M.Z., Anuar, N.S.M. (2016), CAD software was used because it could design from sketches to two-dimensional drawing, three-dimensional drawing, technical drawing, rendering process, and animation, and transfer the data to machine to create model item. Therefore, this research was carried out using computer-aided design (CAD) software to improve design quality and to aid in the creation, modification, analysis, or optimization of each design by displaying the overall appearance of the designed jewellery product.

2.2 Generation Ideas for Songket Brooch Designs

Figure 4: The process of making Songket Brooch from subject matter tampuk manggis motif.

3. FINDINGS

Songket Brooch designs are based on the element and principle of design, The development of ideas is made so that the design looks harmonious, creative and innovative without leaving aside the original form of the study material.

By applying the basic techniques of jewellery fabrication and gemstone setting by using the latest manufacturing technology, these elements can be seen through the shape, structure, luster, and color of this brooch. The process of making this brooch also uses three latest technology machines namely multi-directional micro-setting microscope, laser engrave and cutting machine and laser welding machine. The advantage of using these 3 machines allows making this brooch songket faster, neater and saves time.

4. CONCLUSION

Benefit to society is being able to introduce and highlight the uniqueness, beauty and songket weaving of the Malay community through the design of contemporary jewellery using local motifs such as mangosteen tampuk motifs as research material and on behalf of the industry out there by helping and giving options to the local jewelry industry about options that can be lifted, diversified and highlighted as research material for jewelry motifs and designs. Therefore, the product made is original from the design of lecturers and students from the College of Creative Arts and is in the process of MyIPO copyright application.

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